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Exploring the relationship between ancient built environments and external-induced contemplative states: A real-world mobile EEG study

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Abstract:

The aesthetic experience of ancient built environments greatly influences visitor's emotions, behaviors, and can profoundly affect their well-being and pleasure. We emphasize that this experience can induce phenomenological states of a contemplative kind, triggered by external factors in the architectural environment. This paper outlines our methodological approach to explore architectural features that can induce an individual to a contemplative state by selecting the case of the Saharan ancient built environment in the M'zab Valley, situated in the south of Algeria, as our case study. The M'zab Valley is renowned for its unification with the surrounding natural environment and its understated yet captivating beauty. This choice is based on feedback analyses from diverse visitors, including foreign tourists, architects, and locals. They praised the richness of the discovery experience at the Saharan site, describing sensations of calmness, tranquility, and contemplation.

Our approach is interdisciplinary, bridging architecture, neuroscience, and computer vision, serving as a nexus between these disciplines. Understanding such an effect is poorly investigated in the real world, especially in non-sacred built environments. The results will have an important implication on the design of contemplative experiences in ordinary architecture, as these experiences improve cognitive and emotional performance, promote brain plasticity, and provide beneficial effects.

We adopt an ecological enactivist approach to understand the relationship between humans and their environment by focusing on the brain, body, and environment system to interpret aesthetic experiences generated by architecture. We hypothesize that we can nonconsciously reach contemplative states by engaging the human sensorimotor system through exogenous factors that characterize the environment, enhancing attention and inducing contemplative experiences.

We studied the contemplative experience of 20 students who had not visited the site before. Guided along a designated touristic path, they were equipped with a 32-channel mobile EEG system to capture brain activity, a smart band to monitor physiological data, and two monocular wide-angle (GoPro) cameras on a chest strap (one on the left and the other on the right). After the exploration, participants completed a questionnaire to provide a subjective account of their experience.

While empirical evidence regarding the brain dynamic underlying externally induced contemplative states remains limited, preliminary research has suggested a potential connection between these states and the Default Mode Network (DMN). Taking this connection into account in our data analyses, we aim to contribute to the further understanding of the neurobiological substrates of such states.

Using the Structure from Motion (SfM) algorithm, the recorded videos were used to reconstruct the explored environment and track participants' positions. SfM, a photogrammetric technique, creates 3D models from 2D images by analyzing image correspondences to estimate the scene's 3D structure and camera poses. This synchronization enables tracking the participants' physiological and cerebral reactions during movement. The next step involves identifying path sequences where physiological and cerebral reactions indicate potential contemplative states. These sequences will be cross-referenced with quantitative spatial data from 3D isovist analysis and phenomenological data. The ultimate goal is to accurately determine the architectural features that evoke contemplative states.

Data analysis and synchronization. [ZAIR.N (2023)]

The explored path and its different sequences characteristic, [ZAIR.N (2023)]

Participant in Experiment Gear with discreet hoodie head covering for comfort and privacy, the mobility was prioritized for a MoBI approach. [ZAIR.N (2023)]

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